

TITLE: Artificial Intelligence Methods for Early Detection of Oral Cavity Cancers: A global survey

Mathias Pascal MBAGA^{1} & Idy DIOP²*

1- LIMBI, Student, ESP/UCAD, Dakar, SENEGAL

2- LIMBI, Full Professor ESP/UCAD, Dakar, SENEGAL

** Email : pascalmbaga@gmail.com*

Abstract:

Oral cavity cancers are often diagnosed at advanced stage due to limited awareness and lack of early screening, leading to poor outcomes and costly treatments. The consequences caused by the disorder of the oral cavity can be highly disabling, leading to social reclusion. However, specialists categorically state that early treatment allows for complete recovery from most malignant oral lesions. To tackle the challenge of early detection, Artificial Intelligence is increasingly at the forefront, emerging as a promising solution through image analysis. Thanks to machine learning and deep learning algorithms, it enables features extraction that allow for advanced classification of lesions. This systematic review was conducted using PRISMA guidelines, covering studies from databases such as PubMed Central, MDPI, IEEE Xplore, BMC, ResearchGate and Google Scholar. The eligible studies reported on AI-based methods for detecting and classifying oral cancers, with a focus on machine learning, deep learning, convolutional neural networks (CNNs), and transformers just to name a few. The findings highlight that CNN-based models remain highly effective for detecting and classifying oral lesions, particularly Oral Squamous Cell Carcinoma (OSCC). However, recent advances show that transformer-based models increasingly match or even surpass CNNs in accuracy and generalizability. In addition, lightweight and mobile-friendly AI systems demonstrate strong potential for remote diagnosis and use in resource-limited situations. This shows the high importance of AI in oral oncology with AI agents becoming indispensable tools. Overall, AI has become essential for oral cancer detection, making early diagnosis more accessible and reducing disparities in early detection. One most promising future direction involves hybrid models that combine CNNs and transformers for improved performance.

Keywords:

Oral Cavity Cancer, Lesion, Early detection, Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Deep Learning.